

Some new organothallium(III) molecular adducts with oxime-hydrazone

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Six organothallium(III) molecular adducts of the type $\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl}_2\cdot\text{L}$ and $\text{PhTlCl}_2\cdot\text{L}$ (where L = oxime-hydrazone ligand) have been synthesized and characterized to established their geometry.

Oxime-hydrazone have mixed functional groups (two-in-one) viz. oxime and hydrazones¹. The survey of literature, reveals that molecular adducts of organothallium(III) with oxime-hydrazone are not yet known². We report herein the synthesis and characterization of $\text{PhTlCl}_2\cdot\text{L}$ and $\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl}_2\cdot\text{L}$ molecular adducts (where L = diacetylmonoxime) benzoylhydrazone (DMBH), diacetylmonoxime isonicotinoyl hydrazone (DMIH) and benzil- α -monoxime isonicotinoyl hydrazone (BMIH) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Oxime-hydrazone.

- (I) R = CH₃, X = CH (DMBH)
(II) R = CH₃, X = N (DMIH)
(III) R = C₆H₅, X = N (BMIH)

Results and discussion

The new synthesised molecular adducts are light in colour and are stable at room temperature even on long

Table 1. Analytical data for $\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl}_2\cdot\text{L}$ and $\text{PhTlCl}_2\cdot\text{L}$ complexes

Complex	% Found (Calcd.)			Molar conductance in acetone $\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$
	C	H	N	
$\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl}_2\cdot\text{DMBH}$	45.2 (45.0)	3.6 (3.7)	6.6 (6.8)	30
$\text{PhTlCl}_2\cdot\text{DMBH}$	35.6 (35.6)	3.0 (3.1)	7.2 (7.3)	34
$\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl}_2\cdot\text{DMIH}$	44.2 (44.3)	3.4 (3.6)	7.2 (7.0)	35
$\text{PhTlCl}_2\cdot\text{DMIH}$	34.0 (34.4)	3.2 (3.0)	7.2 (7.5)	22
$\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl}_2\cdot\text{BMIH}$	53.2 (53.0)	3.4 (3.5)	5.6 (5.8)	24
$\text{PhTlCl}_2\cdot\text{BMIH}$	45.6 (45.7)	3.2 (3.0)	6.0 (6.1)	32

standing. The elemental analyses and molar conductance data are listed in Table 1. The low molar conductance of the complexes indicates that they are non electrolyte³.

IR spectra of DMBH, DMIH and BMIH showed bands at 3325, 3175, 3390, 1768, 1671, 1676, 1640–1650 and 1017, 1027, 930 cm^{-1} respectively assigned to νOH (oxime), $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ and $\nu\text{N}-\text{O}$ vibrations¹. IR spectra of all prepared molecular adducts exhibited $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ band at 1620–1610 cm^{-1} which appeared at 1640–1650 cm^{-1} in the free ligands. The lowering of this band in the complexes indicates the coordination of nitrogen atoms of azomethine groups to the thallium^{4,5}, νOH (oxime) and $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ were found unchanged in both ligand and prepared molecular adducts, suggesting non-involvement of oxygen of oxime

and $-\text{C}-$ group to the thallium metal ion^{4,5}. The far IR spectra exhibited bands at 600–200 cm^{-1} for $\nu\text{Tl}-\text{C}$.

It was noticed that the binding energy of Tl 4f in the starting material PhTlCl_2 or Ph_2TlCl_2 was higher than their prepared molecular adducts. These observations concluded

Fig. 2. N1s Photoelectron spectra of DMBH ligand and $\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl}_2\cdot\text{DMBH}$ molecular adduct.

that the electron density of Tl metal ion has been increased by the coordination of Schiff base ligands with thallium metal ion⁶. The N1s photoelectron peak in all these prepared molecular adducts have shown two symmetrical peaks in intensity ratio 2 : 1; with one higher binding energy than parent ligands and another with same in binding energy as in free ligand and with lower intensity; suggesting two nitrogen atoms of Schiff base ligand are coordinated to thallium metal ion and one nitrogen atom is uncoordinated⁶ (Fig. 2, Table 2).

Table 2. T14f, N1s and O1s binding energies (eV) in $\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl.L}$ and $\text{PhTlCl}_2\text{.L}$ complexes

Sl. no	Complex	T14f	N1s	O1s
1.	Ph_2TlCl	119.6	–	–
2.	PhTlCl_2	119.8	–	–
3.	DMBH	–	400.8	532.4
4.	$\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl.DMBH}$	116.2	400.8–402.4	532.4
5.	$\text{PhTlCl}_2\text{.DMBH}$	116.4	400.8–402.2	532.4
6.	DMIH	–	400.8	532.4
7.	$\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl.DMIH}$	116.2	400.6–402.4	532.4
8.	$\text{PhTlCl}_2\text{.BMIH}$	116.2	400.8–402.2	532.4
9.	BMIH	–	400.6	532.4
10.	$\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl.BMIH}$	116.2	400.6–402.0	532.4
11.	$\text{PhTlCl}_2\text{.BMIH}$	116.2	400.6–402.0	532.4

It was also observed that O1s binding energy in $\text{PhTlCl}_2\text{.L}$ or $\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl.L}$ (where L = ligand) molecular adducts were same as their ligands. These observation concluded that oxygen atom of ligand is not bonded with thallium metal ion⁶. On the basis of elemental analyses, con-

Fig. 3. (a) $\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl.L}$, (b) $\text{PhTlCl}_2\text{.L}$ (where L = ligand).

ductivity data, IR and X-ray photoelectron (XPS) data identifying the site of coordination, it is possible to conclude that $\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl.L}$ and $\text{PhTlCl}_2\text{.L}$ are trigonal bipyramidal (Fig. 3).

Experimental

PhTlCl_2 ⁷, Ph_2TlCl ⁸ and all ligands¹ were synthesized and characterized by reported methods.

Preparation of $\text{PhTlCl}_2\text{.L}$ and $\text{Ph}_2\text{TlCl.L}$ complexes :

A mixture of PhTlCl_2 or Ph_2TlCl (1 mmol) in dry CHCl_3 and ligand (1 mmol) was refluxed (~3 h). The solid was obtained after rotary evaporation, was purified by pet-ether (b.p. 60–80°) and air-dried. The micro-analysis of the complexes were carried out at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Conductances were measured in acetone at RT using a Digisun electronic conductivity bridge. IR spectra (CsI) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 457 spectrophotometer. The X-ray photoelectron spectra were recorded on VG Scientific ESCA-3MK-II electron spectrometer.

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